

Shedding electrons on ADOR zeolite structures – Structure determination by 3DED

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ABSTRACT

Three-dimensional electron diffraction (3DED) offers a powerful alternative to single-crystal X-ray diffraction (SCXRD) for the structure determination of crystalline materials with small-sized crystals (usually nanometre-sized) or crystals with intergrowths, often produced during zeolite synthesis. ADOR is a synthesis strategy of novel daughter zeolites from well-known parent germanosilicates. Structure determination of such ADOR zeolites is challenging due to the presence of aggregated intergrowths, and often small-sized crystals. This work demonstrates the application of continuous rotation electron diffraction (cRED), a type of 3DED, for the rapid structural characterisation of zeolites produced by ADOR approach. cRED can be performed in a transmission electron microscope and the structure of a studied material can be obtained rapidly. We propose a unified workflow for the structure determination of ADOR daughter materials. This workflow involves the initial structural investigation and determination of the parent material, followed by the utilization of this knowledge to facilitate the subsequent structure determination of the daughter material. Investigation strategy was shown to be uniform, as presented for ADOR transformation of two different parent germanosilicates. This approach is a tool allowing prompt recognition of new ADOR zeolites at the early stage of their synthesis and can be used for a feedback-based optimisation of synthesis conditions.

1. Introduction

Zeolites are crystalline elementosilicates with a three-dimensional framework consisting of TO₄ tetrahedra (where T represents a heteroatom like Si, Al, Ga, Ge, or others), which are connected via oxygen bridges [1]. This framework creates a network of micropores and cavities, offering a high surface area and exceptional chemical and thermal stability. These unique properties render zeolites suitable for various applications such as catalysts (e.g., in refining processes and petrochemistry [2]), sorbents and ion exchangers [3–5]. Due to these wide applications, knowledge about the structure of new synthesized zeolites is crucial. Often, structure solution by standard methods is challenging due to the properties of synthesized crystal. Zeolite synthesis often produce polycrystalline materials with nanosized crystals that are typically challenging to analyse using single-crystal X-ray diffraction (SCXRD). While powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) is commonly used, structure determination can be time-consuming and challenging due to overlapping reflections with similar d-spacing. This overlap may restrict

options to determine minor differences in the structure of parent and daughter materials [6–9].

While hydrothermal synthesis remains the most common method for preparing zeolites [2], other approaches have emerged. One of such way is the ADOR approach, which offers a selective and controllable way to disassemble the 3D framework of a parent zeolite into layered building units [10,11]. These units can then be reorganized and reassembled to create new daughter zeolite structures [10]. ADOR process begins with the preparation of an initial parent zeolite by hydrothermal synthesis (Assembly step). Parent materials are germanosilicates, having germanium-rich D4R units in their structures, such as zeolites with UTL, UOV, or IWW topology [11,12]. The synthesized parent zeolite is then transformed into 2D layers by hydrolysis of germanium-rich units (Disassembly step). This is followed by the rearrangement of these layers into suitable orientations, e.g. by intercalation with organic agents (Organization step). Finally, these layers are condensed by calcination back together to form the new daughter zeolite structure (Reassembly step) [5,10,13].

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Herein we present a novel approach to determining the structures of ADORable zeolites using continuous rotation electron diffraction (cRED). Development of this technique motivated us to utilize electron diffraction for investigation of ADOR zeolites, which allows us to get a structure solution fast [14]. cRED is one of the 3D electron diffraction methods, where the sample is continuously rotated within the whole goniometer range (usually approximately 120°) of a transmission electron microscope (TEM). This method uses electrons instead of X-rays as radiation source, leveraging the fact that electrons interact with matter stronger, allowing single-crystal diffraction experiments on crystals with dimensions on the nanoscale [15–18]. However, it is important to acknowledge that a drawback of this technique is the possibility of beam damage, especially in case of electron beam-sensitive materials, such as zeolites. The selected crystal of a sample is tilted in the range of the TEM goniometer during the 3DED measurements, which maximize completeness of the data, and the multiple scattering is reduced compared to still zone axis ED. The outcome of one measurement is the data set, which consists set of diffraction patterns at different tilt angles. The data treatment is achieved with the well-developed programs, same as for X-ray diffraction without any treatment for multiple scattering [15].

Our approach focusses on structure determination of UTL-derived zeolites by cRED. It is based on the similarities between the parent and daughter materials. We synthesized UTL zeolite as a parent material [19,20]. It is an extra-large pore germanosilicate with 14- and 12- ring channels and it has double-four rings (D4Rs) as a connecting unit between its layers. These D4Rs are rich with Ge [10] and as such, removable by hydrolysis during the disassembly step resulting in separated layers of the parental structure. Product of this hydrolysis is the 2D layered precursor (IPC-1P), which can be reorganized in a variety of ways and reassembled by calcination to form other 3D zeolites (daughter materials). We prepared IPC-2 (OKO) [21] and IPC-4 (PCR) as daughter materials of UTL [22]. These materials vary in their different types of units connecting their layers. IPC-2 has single-four rings (S4Rs) as a connecting unit that form 10- and 12-ring channels. IPC-4 contains oxygen bridges between layers, and thus it creates smaller 8- and 10-ring channels [10,23]. Further, we show that the presented approach is uniform by the case study of the ADOR transformation of different parent germanosilicate.

2. Experimental

2.1. Synthesis of structure-directing agent (SDA)

2,6-dimethyl-5-azoniaspiro[4.5]decane bromide was chosen as the structure-directing agent (SDA) for the synthesis of UTL. Following the reported procedure [24], a mixture of 30 ml of 1,4-dibrombutane (0.25 mol, 1 eq), 41.5 g of K_2CO_3 (0.3 mol, 1.2 eq), and 640 ml of acetonitrile was stirred. 35 ml of 2,6-dimethylpiperidine (0.25 mol, 1 eq) was then added dropwise using a dropping funnel. The reaction mixture was refluxed overnight. Subsequently, the solvent was removed using a rotary evaporator. The reaction product was dissolved in ethanol (approx. 400 ml) and filtered to remove K_2CO_3 . The filtrate was evaporated to get a saturated solution. Excess diethyl ether was added to precipitate a white solid, which was isolated by filtration and washed with diethyl ether. The final product, 6-azonia-spiro[5.5]undecane bromide, was air dried overnight and its purity confirmed by NMR. The yield was 48.2 g.

Synthesized SDA was ion-exchanged. Prior to the ion exchange, Ambersep 900 resin in hydroxide form was washed with distilled water. Then 39.4 g of the SDA was dissolved in 200 ml of distilled water. The resin was then added (doubled the amount of SDA) to the SDA solution, and the mixture was stirred for 3.5 h. Finally, the resin was separated from the solution by filtration.

2.2. Synthesis of UTL parent material

19.1 g of SiO_2 (0.32 mol, 1 eq) and 16.6 g of GeO_2 (0.16 mol, 0.5 eq) were added to the SDA solution. The mixture was stirred again for about 40 min. The resulting gel with pH 11 was then transferred to autoclaves. The synthesis was performed in a rotation oven at $175^\circ C$ for 10 days. The mixture was then filtered and washed with distilled water until pH 7 was reached. The final product was dried overnight at $60^\circ C$ and then calcined for 6 h at $550^\circ C$ with a rate of $1^\circ C$ per minute [25]. The yield was 28.4 g.

2.3. Synthesis of daughter materials

The first daughter material, IPC-2, was synthesized via the inverse sigma transformation route [5]. Calcined UTL parent material was hydrolysed using 12M HCl. 1 g of UTL was mixed with 160 ml of HCl and this mixture was refluxed at $100^\circ C$ for 24 h. The obtained solid product was isolated by filtration and washed with distilled water until pH 7 was reached. Finally, the sample was dried overnight at $60^\circ C$ in an oven and then calcined at $550^\circ C$ for 6 h with temperature rate of $1^\circ C$ per minute. The yield was 0.7 g.

The synthesis the second daughter material, IPC-4, involved the hydrolysis of UTL to 2D layered precursor (IPC-1P). UTL (1 g) was mixed with 1M CH_3COOH (200 ml) and the mixture was refluxed at $75^\circ C$ overnight. The obtained product, IPC-1P, was isolated by filtration, washed with distilled water, and dried at $60^\circ C$. Subsequently, synthesized IPC-1P (0.4 g) was mixed with 1-octylamine (32 ml). The reaction mixture was heated under reflux at $70^\circ C$ for 7 h, followed by overnight stirring at room temperature without any heating. The final product was isolated by centrifugation and then dried in the oven at $60^\circ C$. Finally, the IPC-4 daughter material was obtained by calcination under the same conditions used for the parent material [22]. The yield was 0.3 g.

3. Methods

The structure and crystallinity of the synthesized samples were first investigated by X-ray powder diffraction using a Bruker AXS D8 Advance powder diffractometer equipped with a LYNXEYE-XE detector using $Cu K\alpha$ radiation in Bragg-Brentano geometry.

The shape and morphology of the prepared samples were examined by SEM using a JEOL IT-800 scanning electron microscope equipped with a field-emission gun operating at 1 kV. Secondary electrons were used for imaging in the charge-free mode.

STEM-EDS was used for imaging and elemental mapping. These measurements were performed using a JEOL JEM NEOARM-200F microscope equipped with a Schottky-type field emission gun operating at 200 keV. Images were collected using an annular dark field detector. JEOL JED-2300 EDS spectrometer was used for elemental analysis.

Textural properties of prepared materials, including total surface area and pore volume, were measured on Micromeritics 3Flex volumetric Surface Area Analyzer. Argon was chosen for these sorption measurements. Prior to analysis, all samples were degassed by heating at $250^\circ C$ for 8 h on a Micromeritics Smart Vac Prep.

Structure determination of ADORable materials was performed using cRED on a JEOL JEM NEOARM-200F transmission electron microscope, equipped with a TVIPS CMOS XF-416 detector. Samples were prepared for cRED by drop casting. Approximately 1 mg of the sample was ground and dissolved in ethanol. The resulting suspension was sonicated to ensure good particle distribution, and a single drop was deposited onto a carbon-coated copper grid. After evaporation of ethanol in air, the grid was loaded onto a high-tilt tomography TEM holder. Following microscope alignment, suitable single-crystals (thin, not surrounded by other crystals, without any other phases, and not at the edge of the grid) were found and measured by cRED. Data were collected using the python software instamatic [26] version 1.7.0 together with EMMenu 5.0.21.0. The holder was tilted within a whole goniometer range, typically from

Fig. 1. PXRD patterns of synthesized zeolites: UTL (green), IPC-2 (red), and IPC-4 (blue).

-70° to $+70^\circ$.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Structural investigation of ADOR materials

The measured powder X-ray diffraction patterns of all samples (Fig. 1) were compared to theoretical patterns from the IZA database, confirming the targeted zeolite framework topologies for each material. Tracking the successful ADOR is possible by the analysis of the positions of the dominant interlayer peak (200). The positions of this peak for UTL, IPC-2, and IPC-4 were observed at 6.1° , 7.7° , and 9.6° , respectively, corresponding to d-spacings of 1.45 nm, 1.15 nm and 0.92 nm [27]. This confirms the successful hydrothermal synthesis of parent UTL germanosilicate as well as transformation of it into two different daughter zeolites by ADOR approach confirming previously presented data [27].

The measured PXRD patterns were fitted by the Le Bail method implemented in the Jana2020 [28] program using published unit cell parameters (from IZA database [29]) as starting values (Fig. 2). The obtained unit cell parameters are summarized in Tables 2–4.

4.2. Morphology of prepared materials

All our samples show similar morphology of the crystals (Fig. 3),

Fig. 2. PXRD patterns of UTL (a), IPC-2 (b) and IPC-4 (c) fitted using the Le Bail method with obtained R_w values.

Table 1
Crystallographic details and statistical information about UTL, IPC-2, and IPC-4.

	UTL	IPC-2	IPC-4
Number of investigated particles	20	17	10
Data for the most complete data set:			
Number of frames	491	418	353
Rotation angle [°]	129.67	113.66	96.87
Data completeness [%]	82.7	55.3	69.2
Resolution limit [Å]	0.8	0.8	0.95
R1 [%]	15.38	18.71	13.15
Crystal system	monoclinic	monoclinic	monoclinic
Space group	$C2/m$	$C2/m$	$C2/m$

Table 2
Unit cell lengths and angles for UTL, parent material.

UTL	a	b	c	α	β	γ
cRED	30.240 (120)	14.312 (6)	12.569 (14)	90.000 (0)	105.318 (170)	90.000 (0)
LeBail	29.761 (5)	14.011 (2)	12.416 (2)	90.000 (0)	104.91 (0)	90.000 (0)
IZA [29]	29.800	13.993	12.939	90.000	105.185	90.000
experimental [19]	29.811 (4)	14.006 (1)	12.402 (1)	90.000 (0)	105.24 (1)	90.000 (0)

Table 3
Unit cell lengths and angles for IPC-2.

IPC-2	a	b	c	α	β	γ
cRED	24.644 (37)	13.924 (9)	12.429 (22)	90.000 (0)	109.756 (160)	90.000 (0)
LeBail	24.360 (9)	13.964 (5)	12.419 (5)	90.000 (0)	109.128 (0)	90.000 (0)
IZA [29]	24.132	13.792	12.298	90.000	109.600	90.000
experimental [21]	24.64	13.92	12.26	90.00	109.20	90.00

Table 4
Unit cell lengths and angles for IPC-4.

IPC-4	a	b	c	α	β	γ
cRED	19.994 (51)	13.802 (31)	12.174 (28)	90.000 (0)	114.479 (220)	90.000 (0)
LeBail	18.210 (10)	13.611 (7)	12.155 (5)	90.000 (0)	114.656 (0)	90.000 (0)
IZA [29]	20.114	13.956	12.351	90.000	114.800	90.000
experimental [22]	20.36	14.17	12.46	90.00	114.09	90.00

Fig. 3. SEM images of plate-like crystals of UTL (a), IPC-2 (b), and IPC-4 (c).

Fig. 4. STEM images (left column) and EDS elemental maps (middle columns, silicon: red; germanium: green) of UTL (a), IPC-2 (b) and IPC-4 (c) with corresponding EDS spectra (right column, additionally, oxygen $K\alpha$ signal: blue, and copper $L\alpha$ signal: grey, were indicated). Cu signal is a background generated by the TEM grid.

which suggest that the ADOR process preserves the morphology of the parent material. The images revealed plate-like crystals stacked upon each other. Notably, the SEM images depict the presence of aggregates, rendering these materials unsuitable for analysis by SCXRD. There have been attempts to separate these aggregates by the severe grinding of the crystals, but unfortunately all of them were unsuccessful. The information about crystal particle size and shape helped us afterwards with the STEM and ED measurements.

4.3. Elemental analysis and high-resolution imaging

Consistent with the SEM observations, STEM also revealed the presence of plate-like crystals in all samples. EDS confirmed a uniform distribution of silicon and germanium within the samples. The Si/Ge ratio in UTL parent material is 4.2. However, EDS also detected a significant decrease in the germanium content for both daughter materials, aligning with the expectations of germanium removal during disassembly step of the ADOR approach (Fig. 4). Based on EDS analysis, the

Fig. 5. Argon sorption isotherms for UTL (green), IPC-2 (red) and IPC-4 (blue).

amount of germanium residues in the daughter materials was estimated as less than 1 wt% of this element in the final samples. The Si/Ge ratio increases significantly for both daughter materials with values of 381.3 for IPC-2 and 658 for IPC-4. This is with good agreement with the data published before [27].

4.4. Description of textural properties of ADOR zeolites

The measured argon adsorption-desorption isotherms (Fig. 5) can be classified as type I(a), which is characteristic for microporous materials. The isotherm for IPC-2 contains a hysteresis loop visible at higher relative pressures, which indicates presence of mesopores. It is probably caused, in case of this particular sample, by interparticle adsorption arising from the crystals existing as aggregates, as observed in the SEM images. BET surface area analysis revealed the highest value for UTL material ($507 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$), followed by IPC-2 ($416 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) and IPC-4 ($225 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$). The total micropore volume shows the same trend, with UTL exhibiting the highest value ($0.21 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$), followed by IPC-2 ($0.16 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) and IPC-4 ($0.07 \text{ cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$). Presented textural data are in good agreement with previously published reports about investigated

materials, where the changes or porosity can be additional factor to track to recognized newly synthesized ADOR daughter zeolite. Generally, the lower surface areas and pore volumes than those for parent material, together with the preservation of micropore character of material are indicators of successful ADOR synthesis of daughter zeolite, however it should be taken as a complementary proof.

4.5. Electron diffraction as a tool for facile structure determination of ADOR zeolites

The collected data were processed by the TVIPS python script contained within instamatic software. REDp [30] was used to reconstruct the 3D reciprocal lattice and for assessment of possible space groups. XDS [31] was utilized for data reduction and integration of diffraction frames. SHELXT [32,33] was used to solve the structure of the materials, and all data were refined with SHELXL [32] within the OLEX2 [34] program. Information about collected data are summarized in Table 1.

The investigation of merged ED patterns by REDp program revealed a C-centered monoclinic Bravais lattice, which corresponds to the $2/m$ Laue class. The reflection conditions were same for parent and daughter materials as well. The conditions are $h + k$ for $(hk0)$, h for $(h0l)$, and k for $(0kl)$. Based on these conditions, the possible space groups for synthesized materials were identified as $C2$, Cm , or $C2/m$. A structure solution of UTL and both daughter materials was found in space group $C2/m$, according to previously published reports (Tables 2–4).

Obtained unit cell parameters of UTL and its two daughter zeolites are shown in Tables 2–4. Discrepancies are observed between values from Le Bail fitting, IZA database and cRED measurement. There are several factors for these differences. The IZA database values are based on model structures containing only silicon and oxygen, and they were obtained from a DLS-refinement [35] in the highest possible symmetry of the framework type. On the other hand, values from Le Bail fitting are gained from the PXRD data, measuring the bulk, powder sample instead of analysing individual single crystals as is the case for cRED. Experimental values represent unit cell parameters obtained from the first reported structures.

Detailed cRED data for this set of materials are presented in Supplementary Information (Tables S1–S6).

Fig. 6–8. illustrated the refined structures and their corresponding pore sizes. The achieved R_1 factors for UTL, IPC-2, and IPC-4 were 15.38 %, 18.71 %, and 13.15 %, respectively. VESTA [36] software was utilized to analyse pore sizes. UTL framework possess 14-ring channels

Fig. 6. Refined structure of UTL (left) and the pore size (right) of 14-ring channel (a) and 12-ring channel (b).

Fig. 7. Refined structure of IPC-2 (left) and the pore size (right) of 12-ring channel (a) and 10-ring channel (b).

Fig. 8. Refined structure of IPC-4 (left) and its pore size (right) of 10-ring channel (a) and 8-ring channel (b).

orientated along c-axis ($10.32 \text{ \AA} \times 13.35 \text{ \AA}$), and 12-ring channels along the b-axis ($8.86 \text{ \AA} \times 11.24 \text{ \AA}$). IPC-2 framework contains 12-ring ($10.76 \text{ \AA} \times 10.46 \text{ \AA}$) along c-axis and 10-ring ($9.18 \text{ \AA} \times 8.50 \text{ \AA}$) pore channels along the b-axis. IPC-4 framework contains the smallest pores with 10 ring ($7.84 \text{ \AA} \times 8.86 \text{ \AA}$) and 8-ring ($7.47 \text{ \AA} \times 5.92 \text{ \AA}$) channels. The presented structures are in the good agreement with the structural data published in the literature. Detailed comparison of unit cell parameters for each structure is presented in Tables 2–3, showing the good match with originally presented experimental data, as well as with the officially approved structures by IZA.

We concluded, that the data collection and further structure determination of ADOR daughter materials by cRED is much more precise and facile when this analysis was firstly done for the parent zeolite. This workflow was used then for a case study of structure determination of different pair of ADORable parent germanosilicate and daughter, novel ADOR zeolite to show that this approach can be standardized for investigation of further, previously unknown structures prepare by this synthesis method. For our investigation we have chosen recently published IPC-20 material prepared from IWV parent germanosilicate [37].

4.6. IPC-20 structure determination: case study

To confirm the validity of this workflow, a study of another parent germanosilicate was performed. We investigated IWV zeolite and its recently reported daughter material denoted as IPC-20 [37]. Up to date, the structure model of IPC-20 has not been recognized and approved by IZA structure commission as unique framework topology. Nevertheless, to our best knowledge it was not reported prior to mentioned study [37]. We selected this material for the structural investigation to demonstrate the versatility of the prepared workflow in terms of use of different parent/daughter zeolite pair on the most recent example of ADOR zeolite synthesis. This is an example showing that the proposed approach is a prompt feedback-based tool that will bolster our constant efforts on the synthesis of new ADOR zeolites from various parent germanosilicates. The whole process started with analysing the parent material (IWV) by common characterization techniques as in the case of UTL to gain the knowledge about the crystallinity, morphology, and textural properties. The results from these analyses are summarized in Fig. 9. According to the established workflow, the analysis of a parent material was a base for the investigation of IPC-20 daughter zeolite, especially for the selection of suitable crystals to be analysed by electron diffraction. Afterwards, the cRED measurement was performed as

Fig. 9. PXRD patterns and argon sorption isotherms for parent IWV (orange, brown for theoretical pattern) and daughter IPC-20 (violet) material. Morphology of IWV (a) and IPC-20 (b) is presented in SEM images.

Table 5

Crystallographic details and statistical information about IWV and IPC-20.

	IWV	IPC-20
Number of investigated particles	10	7
Data for the most complete data set:		
Number of frames	414	497
Rotation angle [°]	111.84	134.03
Data completeness [%]	81.1	80.6
Resolution limit [Å]	0.9	0.8
R1 [%]	21.34	20.78
Crystal system	orthorhombic	orthorhombic
Space group	<i>Fmmm</i>	<i>Fmm2</i>

Table 6

Unit cell parameters of IWV, parent material.

IWV	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	α	β	γ
cRED	13.684(15)	25.209(7)	28.305(24)	90.000(0)	90.000(0)	90.000(0)
LeBail	14.538(1)	25.864(3)	27.523(3)	90.000(0)	90.000(0)	90.000(0)
IZA [29]	13.944	26.081	27.826	90.000	90.000	90.000
experimental [38]	13.7923(4)	25.2969(7)	27.7508(5)	90.000(0)	90.000(0)	90.000(0)

Table 7

Unit cell parameters of IPC-20, daughter material.

IPC-20	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>c</i>	α	β	γ
cRED	13.575(6)	22.303(6)	24.914(7)	90.000(0)	90.000(0)	90.000(0)
LeBail	13.777(1)	22.772(1)	25.238(2)	90.000(0)	90.000(0)	90.000(0)
CCDC ^a , [39]	13.8124(19)	22.711(6)	25.356(4)	90.0(0)	90.0(0)	90.0(0)

^a Refined experimental data for IPC-20 were used for CCDC input.

Fig. 10. Refined structures of IWV (a) and IPC-20 (b).

Fig. 11. Scheme of established workflow of structure determination of ADORable zeolites by cRED.

respectively. The detailed cRED data for this set of materials are presented in Tables S7–S10.

Based on the observed similarities, we achieved fast and reliable, as confirmed by the comparison with literature data (Tables 6 and 7), structure determination process for IPC-20 daughter material. The refined structures of IWV and IPC-20 are shown in Fig. 10., where R_1 factor for IWV was 21.34 % and 20.78 % for IPC-20.

This study has successfully established a workflow for the rapid and reliable structure determination of ADOR materials using advanced characterization technique. Leveraging the capabilities of cRED, we have determined the structures of well-known ADOR materials. Our approach, involving a combination of basic characterization techniques and 3DED analysis, has proven to be efficient and effective in structure determination of ADOR daughter materials. The primary advantage of this workflow lies in its speed, enabling us to promptly confirm the structures of ADOR-derived zeolites immediately following synthesis by leveraging the similarities with their parent materials. The workflow is schematically depicted in Fig. 11. This makes our approach a powerful synthesis tool providing an instant feedback for the experimentalist, that might be used for spotting new structures or tuning the synthesis

conditions towards the synthesis of new materials.

To validate this approach, we focused on the well-known materials. We began with UTL and its daughter materials (IPC-2 and IPC-4). The whole process started with examination of parent material's morphology, crystallinity and textural properties, followed by 3DED structure determination. By comparing the daughter materials to the parent, we found several similarities in their structures, that simplified the structure determination process afterwards. To prove this concept, we continued with another parent (IWV) and its daughter material (IPC-20). The prior characterization of IWV simplified the further structure determination of IPC-20. These experiments showed us, that this workflow can be used also for another ADOR daughter zeolites and we can achieve faster structure determination compared to commonly used determination from PXRD.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we have demonstrated the effectiveness of a unified workflow for structure determination of ADORable zeolites. By leveraging detailed characterization of the parent material, including

morphology, texture, and elemental composition, we have significantly simplified the subsequent structure determination of daughter materials by cRED technique. This approach was confirmed by study of multiple parent and daughter set of materials showing its consistency and proving the general use in case of structure solution of zeolites prepared by ADOR synthesis.

In the future, we will apply the established workflow to determine the structures of other, more challenging, UTL-derived daughter materials (such as IPC-6 [40], IPC-7 [40], IPC-9 [41], and IPC-10 [41]). These structures are more defective, usually producing lower quality and smaller crystals. Moreover, IPC-6 and IPC-7 are materials with alternating layer connectivity more challenging for structure investigation. Nevertheless, the presented workflow is a prompt and valuable tool at the synthesis stage for the fast and facile verification of crystal structure of such potentially new ADOR zeolites. Moreover, other ADORable parent zeolites [42] are still under investigation for possibly producing novel daughter materials, thus the presented approach will be utilized as a standard, fast track, structural characterisation of ADOR zeolites during their synthesis optimisation in the future. We clearly presented that in the case of zeolites prepared by ADOR, when compared to PXRD, cRED offers significantly faster identification of unknown structures.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Anna Laštovicková: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Daniel N. Rainer:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Michal Mazur:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2025.113514>.

Data availability

All data are available in Zenodo open archive under the link: <https://zenodo.org/records/14718810>. CCDC 2410737-2410741 contain the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/structures.

References

- [1] W.H. Baur, R.X. Fischer, The flexibility of the T–X–T hinges between the coordination tetrahedra in various zeolitic frameworks: an empirical structural study, *Mineral. Petrol.* 117 (2023) 165–179.
- [2] X. Meng, F.S. Xiao, Green routes for synthesis of zeolites, *Chem. Rev.* 114 (2014) 1521–1543.
- [3] W.J. Roth, et al., Two-dimensional zeolites : current status and perspectives, *Chem. Rev.* 114 (2014) 4807–4837.
- [4] Z. Wang, et al., Needs and trends in rational synthesis of zeolitic materials, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 41 (2012) 1729–1741.
- [5] M. Mazur, et al., Germanosilicate UTL and its rich chemistry of solid-state transformations towards IPC-2 (OKO) zeolite, *Catal. Today* 243 (2015) 23–31.
- [6] J. Cho, et al., The synergistic development of electron crystallography and zeolite discovery, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 358 (2023) 112400.
- [7] J. Su, et al., Structure analysis of zeolites by rotation electron diffraction (RED), *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 189 (2014) 115–125.
- [8] Y. Luo, et al., Visualization of Topotactic Structural Transformations of Zeolites Using 3D Electron Diffraction, 2023.
- [9] J. Li, J. Sun, Application of X-ray diffraction and electron crystallography for solving complex structure problems, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 50 (2017) 2737–2745.
- [10] P. Eliášová, et al., The ADOR mechanism for the synthesis of new zeolites, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 44 (2015) 7177–7206.
- [11] S.E. Henkelis, et al., A procedure for identifying possible products in the assembly–disassembly–organization–reassembly (ADOR) synthesis of zeolites, *Nat. Protoc.* 14 (2019) 781–794.
- [12] J. Zhang, et al., Toward controlling disassembly step within the ADOR process for the synthesis of zeolites, *Chem. Mater.* 33 (2021) 1228–1237.
- [13] M. Trachta, et al., The ADOR synthesis of new zeolites: in silico investigation, *Catal. Today* 243 (2015) 32–38.
- [14] T. Willhammar, X. Zou, Stacking disorders in zeolites and open-frameworks - structure elucidation and analysis by electron crystallography and X-ray diffraction, *Z. Kristallogr.* 228 (2013) 11–27.
- [15] M. Gemmi, et al., 3D electron diffraction: the nanocrystallography revolution, *ACS Cent. Sci.* 5 (2019) 1315–1329.
- [16] L.A. Bendersky, F.W. Gayle, Electron diffraction using transmission electron microscopy, *J. Res. Natl. Inst. Stand. Technol* 106 (2001) 997–1012.
- [17] M. Gemmi, A.E. Lanza, 3D electron diffraction techniques, *Acta Crystallogr B Struct Sci Cryst Eng Mater* 75 (2019) 495–504.
- [18] T. Gruene, E. Mugnaioli, 3D electron diffraction for chemical analysis: instrumentation developments and innovative applications, *Chem. Rev.* 121 (2021) 11823–11834.
- [19] J.L. Paillaud, et al., Extra-large-pore zeolites with two-dimensional channels formed by 14 and 12 rings, *Science* 304 (2004) 990–992.
- [20] J. Li, et al., Structure solution and defect analysis of an extra-large pore zeolite with UTL topology by electron microscopy, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 11 (2020) 3350–3356.
- [21] E. Verheyen, et al., Design of zeolite by inverse sigma transformation, *Nat. Mater.* 11 (2012) 1059–1064.
- [22] W.J. Roth, et al., A family of zeolites with controlled pore size prepared using a top-down method, *Nat. Chem.* 5 (2013) 628–633.
- [23] S.A. Morris, et al., Combined PDF and Rietveld studies of ADORable zeolites and the disordered intermediate IPC-1P, *Dalton Trans.* 45 (2016) 14124–14130.
- [24] M.G. Marino, K.D. Kreuer, Alkaline stability of quaternary ammonium cations for alkaline fuel cell membranes and ionic liquids, *ChemSusChem* 8 (2015) 513–523.
- [25] J. Čejka, et al., The role of template structure and synergism between inorganic and organic structure directing agents in the synthesis of utl zeolite, *Chem. Mater.* 22 (2010) 3482–3495.
- [26] Stef Smeets, et al., Instamatic (1.0.0). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2026774>, 2018.
- [27] P. Eliášová, et al., The ADOR mechanism for the synthesis of new zeolites, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 44 (2015) 7177–7206.
- [28] V. Petříček, et al., Jana 2020 - a new version of the crystallographic computing system Jana, *Z. für Kristallogr. - Cryst. Mater.* 238 (2023) 271–282.
- [29] Database of zeolite structures. <http://www.iza-structure.org/databases/>.
- [30] W. Wan, et al., Three-dimensional rotation electron diffraction: software RED for automated data collection and data processing, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* 46 (2013) 1863–1873.
- [31] W.X.D.S. Kabsch, *Acta Crystallogr. D* 66 (2010) 125–132.
- [32] G.M. Sheldrick, A short history of SHELX, *Acta Crystallogr. A* 64 (2008) 112–122.
- [33] G.M. Sheldrick, Shelxt - integrated space-group and crystal-structure determination, *Acta Crystallogr. A* 71 (2015) 3–8.
- [34] O.V. Dolomanov, et al., OLEX2: a complete structure solution, refinement and analysis program, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* 42 (2009) 339–341.
- [35] C. Baerlocher, et al., DLS-76, a Program for the Simulation of Crystal Structures by Geometric Refinement, Institute of Crystallography and Petrography, ETH, 1977.
- [36] K. Momma, F. Izumi, VESTA 3 for three-dimensional visualization of crystal, volumetric and morphology data, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.* 44 (2011) 1272–1276.
- [37] Q. Yue, et al., Catching a new zeolite as a transition material during deconstruction, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 145 (2023) 9081–9091.
- [38] D.L. Dorset, et al., P-derived organic cations as structure-directing agents: synthesis of a high-silica zeolite (ITQ-27) with a two-dimensional 12-ring channel system, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 128 (2006) 8862–8867.
- [39] The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre. <https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/>.

- [40] P.S. Wheatley, et al., Zeolites with continuously tuneable porosity, *Angew. Chem.* 126 (2014) 13426–13430.
- [41] M. Mazur, et al., Synthesis of ‘unfeasible’ zeolites, *Nat. Chem.* 8 (2016) 58–62.
- [42] M. Trachta, et al., The ADOR synthesis of new zeolites: in silico investigation, *Catal. Today* 243 (2015) 32–38.